

GLOBAL CONFLICTS

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Abstract. This article talks about the concept of conflict, its origin, history and current global conflicts, their consequences, mutual disputes and conflicts between countries that are stronger than each other in the world.

Keywords: conflict, political, human, society, movement, ethnic, world, process, destruction, global, union, nation, modernization.

ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ КОНФЛИКТЫ

Аннотация. В этой статье рассказывается о понятии конфликта, его происхождении, истории и текущих глобальных конфликтах, их последствиях, взаимных спорах и конфликтах между странами, которые сильнее друг друга в мире.

Ключевые слова: конфликт, политический, человеческий, общество, движение, этнический, мир, процесс, разрушение, глобальный, союз, нация, модернизация.

Enter. As we live in the current developing era, competition remains an integral part of human being. It is natural that many conflicts will arise after this. It is no exaggeration to say that global conflicts occur in different fields in different countries. A simple example of global conflicts is when two countries compete with each other in the competition of goods and various global conflicts that end with the emergence of negative consequences in the background, and eventually conflict and disagreement between them. may occur. This is not only in the competition of goods, but in general, the society we live in cannot be imagined without conflicts. Conflicts are now becoming a global problem, not only among citizens of the same society, representatives of the same nation, but also among strong developed countries. As a result of this, the states lead to bloody wars based on conflicts with each other. These global conflicts are drying up the pillow of some country, and it is a process that is worthless than the complete decline of the socio-economic development process. Looking at history, we can say that global conflicts will happen before us and after us. Because we live in a society that is developing day by day, conflicts keep blooming like the fruit of a tree. No matter how much the fruit of the tree is cut, new fruits will take root. Global conflicts are similar. No matter how many disputes and conflicts are resolved peacefully, he still continues to show his stature in another field, even if not in that field.

Analysis of literature on the topic (Literature review). It is known that the life of society consists of many interrelated areas. Among them, the largest are economic, social, political and spiritual spheres. Each of these areas develops on the basis of its own development laws and traditions, they have separate systems with their own unique methods of organization and management. Also, each of these areas is studied and researched by its own sciences. The first studies on conflicts belong to the VI-VII centuries BC. At that time, Chinese thinkers wrote that everything that exists is the source of development in mutual relations, in the positive (Yan) and negative (In) aspects inherent in matter, which are in constant opposition to each other, and it is precisely these who own them. causes confrontation (conflict) between them. In ancient Greece, a

philosophical doctrine appeared about opposites and their role in the creation of objects. The Florentine writer Niccolò Machiavelli (1469-1527) was the first to attempt a systematic analysis of conflicts. He considered the conflict to be a universal and continuous state of society due to the selfish nature of man, the desire of various groups for permanent and unlimited wealth. He considers the nobles, who have concentrated all the state power in their hands, to be one of the sources of conflict. The English philosopher Francis Bacon (1561-1626) was the first to conduct a detailed analysis of the system of conflicts within the country.

In the new era, the following ideas of the Geneva philosopher and writer Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1712-1778) about the gradation of the entire world historical process were widely spread: 1) At first, there is a "state of nature" where people are free and equal;

2) Then the development of civilization leads to the loss of equality, freedom and happiness; 3) People who have concluded the "Community Agreement" regain the harmony of social relations that they have lost, and reach an agreement of lifelong peace and harmony; social peace can occur under the strict control of the people, because wars are necessary for situations, and they do not show their good intentions.

Initially, the conflict as a multi-class social phenomenon was studied in the work of the Scottish philosopher Adam Smith (1723-1790) "Inquiry into the nature and causes of public wealth". According to him, the basis of the conflict is the division of society into classes (capitalists, landowners, hired workers) and economic competition. Adam Smith considered the struggle between classes as the source of society's progress, and social conflict as a special blessing for humanity.

The German scientist Immanuel Kant (1724-1804) said "... the state of peace between people living as neighbors is not a natural state, it is, on the contrary, a state of war, that is, if there is no continuous hostile action, it is a constant danger. So, it is necessary to establish a state of peace..." he said. A connection with Rousseau's ideas about the "Social Contract" can be observed here.

According to the German philosopher Georg Hegel (1770-1831), the main cause of the conflict is the social disparity between the "accumulation of wealth" on the one hand, and the "work-bound class" on the other. Hegel was opposed to riots and disturbances affecting the unity of the state within the country. He believed that the state protects the interests of the whole society and conflicts should be coordinated. The problem of the struggle for life occupied a central place in the teachings of the English biologist Charles Darwin (1809-1882). The main idea of Darwin's works is that living nature develops in the conditions of a constant struggle for life, which constitutes a natural selection mechanism for the selection of the best adapted species. Later, Darwin's views were advanced in some sociological and psychological theories of conflict.

Analysis and results (Analysis and results). According to the duration and level of tension, there are types of conflicts:

1) passionate and fast-paced conflicts - they are intense and emotional, they are distinguished by the extremely sharp manifestation of negative relations of the conflict parties, they can reach a difficult conclusion and lead to tragic consequences. They are based on the mental state of people in conflict.;

2) sharp and continuous conflicts - conflicts arise in cases where they are very deep, stable, irreconcilable or very difficult to compromise. The conflicting parties control their situation and actions. Predictions about the solution are also largely uncertain;

3) conflicts that are not well expressed and slow - if such a conflict occurred only in a certain episode, then in these cases it is possible to talk about an acceptable prediction (prognosis). If such a chain of conflicts is formed, the prediction can be not only complicated, but also unpleasant.

Types of conflict according to the degree of organization of social life:

- global;
- regional;
- interstate;
- interethnic;
- between classes or between different classes of society;
- intergroup;
- inter-party;
- interpersonal political, ideological, spiritual

If the number of participating parties, that is, the range of participants, is taken as a criterion, then it can be said that conflicts are two-, three-, and multi-sided. When the level of force pressure is taken as a criterion, conflicts in such cases are divided into non-armed (customs wars) and armed conflicts, which in fact consist of carrying out military actions of various scales. If the level of conflicts is taken as a criterion, it can be said that there are aggressive and compromise types of conflicts. Also, there is a difference between important and non-important issues. But all conflicts cannot be summarized in a single universal scheme. For example, in a conflict in the form of a struggle, the solution can end only with the victory of one of the parties, while in a conflict in the category of discussions, a common compromise can be chosen. From this point of view, conflict resolution can be divided into the following groups:

- resolution and termination of the conflict according to the voluntary agreement of the parties;

- finding and stopping a symmetric solution to the conflict (two

The side either wins or loses in the same way);

- asymmetric resolution of the conflict (only one side wins in the conflict);

- a dispute causes another big dispute;

- the gradual fading away of the conflict.

It seems that, in fact, depending on the resolution of the dispute, it is divided into types

It's division does not include all its existing features.

Because there will be many non-standard situations in the resolution of the dispute.

1) the dispute becomes tense;

2) show violence;

3) peaceful settlement of the conflict.

In other words, the deadlock of the conflict means that "its solution has been suspended for some time", its resolution based on violence means that the parties try to destroy each other, and the peaceful resolution of the conflict means its constructive, i.e. means that the possibility of being

resolved by reason has been used". The consequences depend on the emotional and psychological characteristics of the parties. means that the tension is increasing.

Conclusion and recommendations. In conclusion, we can say that since childhood, the human race has faced various disputes and conflicts in a way that it did not want. If we remember our childhood, we will realize that we were very worried about simple things, we indulged in our feelings and fought for the protection of our interests. There are such conflicting situations in life that a simple thing becomes an excuse, families break up, people go to the point of killing each other, as a result of which someone's life is taken. Later, they cannot explain why he did such actions throughout his life.

If a person says from the first steps of a conflict, "Here are the first signs of a conflict, what consequences can they have, come on, I better save myself from them with my mind", then he has reacted correctly to conflict situations. ladi Because the emotional and psychological mood of the person who starts the conflict can completely change after a minute or two, and he will behave completely differently in another emotional and psychological mood.

Instead of conclusion and proposal, we should emphasize that ethical and aesthetic values are formed in every nation to regulate various relationships between people. Therefore, people are brought up on the basis of national moral values and norms. Every person who has noticed the consequences of conflicts should think about a reasonable response and a reasonable attitude to them, i.e. what are the specifics of the conflicts that are affecting them now and what consequences can they have later? should see and immediately find a solution.

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